

HOW TO CALCULATE THE CARBON FOOTPRINT OF A DIGITAL PRESERVATION SERVICE

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Abstract – We have developed a model for in-body carbon footprint calculation for the national digital preservation services in Finland. This model is based on publicly available data from different vendors. We will elaborate on this model in the workshop and provide a template for calculating the carbon footprint for a group exercise during the workshop. The workshop is targeted at anyone who is interested in estimating the carbon footprint of their service.

Submission Type – Workshop

Keywords – carbon footprint, IT-infrastructure, sustainability

Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental sustainability is nowadays a decisive factor when determining the development of products and services and it is also an important factor in digital preservation. Digital preservation is a long-term activity that should be produced on a stable and sustainable basis, where risk management is central in ensuring that preserved digital content is not at a high risk. In addition to other sustainability factors, managing the environmental impact is of utmost importance, as the needs of the environment can pose constraints on the digital preservation service.

Monitoring the impact of a digital preservation service on the environment is becoming more and more common, with recent conferences having contributions and discussions on this topic [[1][2], [3]]. However, the models and assumptions on how to calculate the carbon footprint for a digital service are different and varied.

In the National Digital Preservation Services in Finland [4], we have created a generic carbon footprint model of our services [5]. This model is created for calculating the carbon footprint in cases where hardware manufacturers do not report the in-body carbon footprint (including hardware manufacturing, logistics and disposal) figures for their hardware. The generic model can be used by any producer of a digital preservation service to calculate their hardware component carbon footprint, without having to have separate in-depth discussions with their hardware manufacturers.

II. SUMMARY OF THE WORKSHOP

The workshop will start with the basics, by introducing a model to calculate the carbon footprint. The calculations of our digital preservation platform will be presented as an example.

The workshop will include a hands-on group session on calculating the carbon footprint of selected preservation services. The calculations will be performed using a spreadsheet developed in our preservation service. We will provide a template for the calculations for the participants.

Because the topic is wide and the participants may have very different digital preservation solutions, room for open discussions is also given.

The target of the workshop is to understand and discuss how a digital preservation platform carbon footprint can be estimated in diverse IT-infrastructure solutions. The workshop will bring new insights to the digital preservation community in general.

The estimated duration of the workshop is two hours, but it can be modified, if needed.

III. AGENDA

1. Introduction: How to calculate the carbon footprint
 - In-body infrastructure carbon footprint
 - Carbon emissions on production life cycle
2. Example: Carbon footprint calculations in the National Digital Preservation Services in Finland
3. Group work on calculating carbon footprint
4. Open discussions on the themes with carbon footprint calculations
5. Conclusions

IV. INTENDED AUDIENCE

The workshop is targeted at all who are interested in estimating the carbon footprint of a digital preservation IT-infrastructure. No previous experience of calculating a carbon footprint is required, but an insight into the infrastructure of one's own platform is beneficial. Participants are recommended to bring their own laptop with a spreadsheet software (e.g., MS Excel) in order to participate actively in the group session, but this is not necessary.

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